

DOI: 10.15276/EJ.02.2024.2
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12746935
 UDC: 331.108; 331.101.3
 JEL: M12, M54

THE INFLUENCE OF WORK DISCIPLINE AND JOB CHARACTERISTICS ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH MOTIVATION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE

ВПЛИВ ТРУДОВОЇ ДИСЦИПЛІНИ ТА ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК РОБОЧОГО МІСЦЯ НА ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ЧЕРЕЗ МОТИВАЦІЮ ЯК ПРОМІЖНУ ЗМІННУ

Asrul Alamsyah Pasaribu
 University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia

Sofiyan
 University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia

Yeni Ariesa
 University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia

Alex Tribuana Sutanto
 University of Prima Indonesia, Medan, Indonesia

Received 17.05.2024

Asrul Alamsyah Pasaribu, Sofiyan, Yeni Ariesa, Alex Tribuana Sutanto. Вплив трудової дисципліни та посадових характеристик на продуктивність працівників через мотивацію як проміжну змінну. Науково-методична стаття.

Ефективність роботи працівників може бути використана як міра успіху компанії. Підтримуючи успіх компанії у здійсненні операційної діяльності, необхідно враховувати, як керівництво компанії управляє людськими ресурсами, в даному випадку працівниками, щоб мати змогу залишатися послідовним у досягненні результатів відповідно до процедур компанії Sanjaya and Saputra (2020). Згідно зі Стірсом та Кунтйоро (2002), організаційна прихильність визначається як почуття ідентифікації (віра в організаційні цінності), залученості (готовність докласти максимум зусиль на благо організації) та лояльності (бажання залишатися членом відповідної організації), висловлене людиною, працівником, по відношенню до своєї організації. Іншими словами, організаційна прихильність – це ставлення, яке відображає лояльність працівників до організації та постійний процес, в якому члени організації спрямовують свою увагу на організацію та її постійний успіх і прогрес.

Ключові слова: людські стосунки, продуктивність, організаційна прихильність, мотивація

Asrul Alamsyah Pasaribu, Sofiyan, Yeni Ariesa, Alex Tribuana Sutanto. The Influence of Work Discipline and Job Characteristics on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable. Scientific and methodical article.

Employee performance can be used as a measure of the success of a company. In supporting the success of a company in carrying out its operational activities, one of the things that needs to be considered is how the management of a company manages employees, in this case employees, to be able to remain consistent in producing performance in accordance with company procedures Sanjaya and Saputra (2020). According to Steers in Kuntjoro (2002), organizational commitment is defined as a sense of identification (belief in organizational values), involvement (willingness to try as best as possible for the benefit of the organization) and loyalty (desire to remain a member of the organization concerned) expressed by a person. employee. towards his organization. In other words, organizational commitment is an attitude that reflects employee loyalty to the organization and an ongoing process in which organizational members divert their attention to the organization and its continued success and progress.

Keywords: human relation, performance, organizational commitment, motivation

Organizational commitment is an important behavioral dimension that can be used to assess an employee's tendency to remain as a member of the organization. Commitment is a person's relatively strong notification and connection to the organization. Employees with high commitment are expected to pay attention to optimal performance. Commitment includes acceptance and belief in the values and goals of the organization, feelings, involvement and a sense of loyalty to the organization. One of the factors that influences performance is the attitude that is reflected in employee behavior in an organization. These attitudes include job satisfaction, job involvement and organizational commitment (Nurandini & Lataruva, 2014). There are several factors that influence employee performance, including job satisfaction, human relations, and organizational commitment (Golung, 2013). These factors influence the employee's methods or tips for completing the work assigned to him, so that the final result is the employee's own performance, whether it will produce good final results or vice versa. Sanjaya and Dewi (2020). According to Hasibuan (2012) job satisfaction refers to the positive perception of employees which is shown by the employee concerned loving his job, where this arises because of the sense of satisfaction obtained from the good management of employees

from company management. Meanwhile, human reality is defined as an interaction between fellow employees and between employees and superiors in a work situation with the aim of encouraging and improving teamwork. Considering the limited time and resources and to clarify the direction of the research, the researcher limited the problem to only Civil Servants (PNS) at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency. Because there are many factors that can influence performance, researchers limit the problem to organizational commitment, human relations and motivation. Theoretically, this research is expected to provide a basis for other researchers in conducting further research related to Human Resource Management, especially in studies of Performance, Organizational Commitment, Human Relations and Motivation. The benefits that can be obtained by the Rantau Selatan Subdistrict Office, Labuhanbatu Regency, from this research are that it can be taken into consideration in decision making, and improve employee performance at the Rantau Selatan Subdistrict Office, Labuhanbatu Regency. The benefit for the author regarding this research is that it is hoped that it can be a means of information from other parties who wish to examine relevant problems in this research.

Every agency or organisation always tries to improve the performance of employees in the hope that the goals will be achieved as expected by an agency / organisation. Employee performance has a very important role in an agency, if the agency has good human resources and has high performance, the goals of the agency can be achieved the goals expected by the agency or organisation.

On the other hand, organisational culture has been created such as professionalism, work discipline and tenacity but still needs to be improved and transmitted to other employees. With a strong organisational culture, organisational commitment will arise which will ultimately increase work productivity, there is also the problem of organisational commitment that there is still low employee commitment to the organisation.

In addition, there are other problems in Human Relations, seen from the low Human Relations at the South Rantau Sub-District Office of Labuhanbatu Regency. This can also be seen from the attitude of employees at the South Rantau Sub-District Office of Labuhanbatu Regency who only carry out their own duties and responsibilities and have no desire to help colleagues who have excessive workloads.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Analysis of recent research and publications. According to Mayer in Notoatmodjo (2015) Performance is a person's success in carrying out a job assigned to him. Meanwhile, according to Gilbert in Notoatmodjo (2015), performance is what a person can do in accordance with their duties and functions. According to Fahmi (2017), "Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements."

According to Nurjaya (2021), performance is the level of achievement of results from carrying out certain tasks. Company performance is the level of achievement of results in order to realize company goals. Furthermore, according to Miner (1990), performance is where a person is expected to function and behave in accordance with the tasks that have been assigned to him. According to Kaswan (2017), organizational commitment is a measure of an employee's willingness to stay with a company in the future. Commitment often reflects an employee's belief in the mission and goals of the organization, a willingness to put forth effort to complete the job and a desire to continue working there. According to Kreitner and Kinicki in Kaswan (2017), organizational commitment reflects how individuals identify themselves with the organization and are bound by its goals. According to Robbins (2008), organizational commitment is a situation where an employee supports a particular organization and its goals and desires to maintain membership in that organization. So high job involvement means siding with an individual's particular job, while high organizational commitment means siding with the organization that recruits that individual. According to Alo (1997), Human Relations is human interpersonal communication, meaning communication that has entered a psychological stage where the communicator and the communicator understand each other's thoughts, feelings and take action together. This also means that if we want to create communication that is full of intimacy which is preceded by the exchange of information about identity and impact on employee self-satisfaction both from economic, psychological and social aspects. According to Danang (2018), motivation talks about how to encourage someone's work enthusiasm, so that they want to work by providing their abilities and expertise optimally to achieve organizational goals. Motivation is important because with motivation it is hoped that every employee will work hard and be enthusiastic to achieve high work productivity Previous research is very important as a basis for preparing this research. The following are the results of previous research conducted by previous researchers that are relevant to this research. personal problems of a social nature. Based on research conducted by Tatan Sutanjar, Oyon Saryono (2019) with the title *The Influence of Employee Motivation, Leadership and Discipline on Employee Performance*, the following research results were obtained: There is an influence of motivation on employee performance, meaning that the higher the motivation, the more employee performance will increase, there is The influence of leadership on employee performance means that the better the leadership, the employee's performance will increase., employee leadership and discipline, employee performance will increase. Based on research conducted by Sumarni, Andri Pramuntadi (2019) with the title *The Influence of Organizational Commitment on Nurse Performance at PK Muhammadiyah Bantul Hospital*, the following research results were obtained which show that there is a positive relationship between organizational climate and professional commitment ($p = 0.001$, $r = 0.326$), so that the hypothesis in this study is accepted. This proves that organizational climate can influence individual behavior which has an impact on professional commitment.

There is a positive influence of the organizational commitment variable on the performance of nurses at PKU Muhammadiyah Bantul Hospital, coefficient of determination ($r = 0.1063$). Thus, the results of this research show that the more positive the organizational climate, the higher the professional commitment, likewise, the more negative the organizational climate, the lower the professional commitment. Based on research conducted by Dewi Astuti (2022) with the title *The Influence of Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance*, the following research results were obtained which show that commitment, both partially and simultaneously, has a significant effect on employee performance, as well as organizational culture, both partially and simultaneously. simultaneously has a significant effect on employee performance. Based on research conducted by Benyamin Richard Manery, Victor P.K. Lengkong, and Regina T. Saerang (2018) with the title *The Influence of Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance in Bkdpsda in North Halmahera Regency*, the following research results showed that simultaneously organizational commitment and culture organization has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Partially, organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance. Partially, organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Based on research conducted by Nurmin Arianto and Hadi Kurniawan (2020) with the title *The Influence of Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance*, the following research results show that motivation and work environment have an influence either partially or simultaneously, while from the correlation results, motivation and work environment has a very strong relationship to performance. Based on research conducted by Hendri Sembiring (2020) entitled *The Influence of Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance at Bank Sinarmas Medan*, the following research results were obtained, namely that motivation and work environment have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Bank Sinarmas Medan. Motivation and work environment explain the influence on the Employee Performance variable (Y) at Bank Sinarmas Medan by 65.3%. Meanwhile, the remaining 34.7% is the influence of other independent variables not examined in this research such as leadership, salary, work stress and so on. To make it easier to explain research, researchers describe a conceptual framework that contains the relationships between variables as follows:

Based on research conducted by Tatan Sutanjar, Oyon Saryono (2019) with the title *The Influence of Employee Motivation, Leadership and Discipline on Employee Performance*, the following research results were obtained: There is an influence of motivation on employee performance, meaning that the higher the motivation, the more employee performance will increase, there is The influence of leadership on employee performance means that the better the leadership, the employee's performance will increase., employee leadership and discipline, employee performance will increase.

Based on research conducted by Nurmin Arianto and Hadi Kurniawan (2020) with the title *The Influence of Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance*, the following research results show that motivation and work environment have an influence either partially or simultaneously, while from the correlation results, motivation and work environment has a very strong relationship to performance. Based on research conducted by Hendri Sembiring (2020) entitled *The Influence of Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance at Bank Sinarmas Medan*, the following research results were obtained, namely that motivation and work environment have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at Bank Sinarmas Medan. Motivation and work environment explain the influence on the Employee Performance variable (Y) at Bank Sinarmas Medan by 65.3%. Meanwhile, the remaining 34.7% is the influence of other independent variables not examined in this research such as leadership, salary, work stress and so on. To make it easier to explain research, researchers describe a conceptual framework that contains the relationships between variables as follows.

The main part

Based on the results of research and discussions conducted by researchers regarding the influence of Organizational Commitment and Human Relations on employee performance at the Rantau Selatan Subdistrict Office through Motivation as an intervening variable, the following conclusions can be drawn.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: authors' own elaboration

Based on the limitations and problem formulation that have been stated previously, the hypothesis of this research is:

1. Organizational Commitment influences employee motivation at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency
2. Human Relations influences employee motivation at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency
3. Organizational Commitment influences employee performance at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency
4. Human Relations influences employee performance at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency
5. Motivation influences employee performance at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency
6. Organizational Commitment influences employee performance at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency through Motivation as an intervening variable.
7. Human Relations influences employee performance at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency through Motivation as an intervening variable.

Research methods. The approach in this research is to use an associative approach, an associative approach is an approach to find out that there is a relationship or influence between the two variables (independent variable and dependent variable). In this research, the independent variable X1 is Organizational Commitment, X2 is Human Relations, Z is Motivation and the dependent variable Y is Performance. According to Morissan (2014: 109) population can be defined as a collection of subjects, variables, concepts or phenomena. We can research each member of the population to find out the characteristics of the population concerned. According to Sugiyono (2018) Population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. The population in this study were all Civil Servants (PNS) at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency, who were recorded in October 2023, totaling 30 people. According to Sugiyono, (2018) The sample is part of the number and characteristics of the population. Because the population is small, the sampling technique in this research is a saturated sample, which means the sample size uses the entire population. In this research, the number of samples used was 30 people.

Table 1. Operational Definitions of Variables

Variable	Defenition	Indikator	Skala
Performance (Y)	Performance is the result of the work process or work success that is expected from an employee which is adjusted to what is stated in the organization's strategic planning and can be measured in quality and quantity within an agreed time frame..	1. Quality 2. Quantity 3. Timeliness 4. Effectiveness of Resource Use 5. Independent 6. Be committed	Likert
Organization Commitment (X ₁)	Organizational commitment is employee willingness which is characterized by a form of loyalty and self-identification with the organization, where employees are willing of their own accord to give the best that is available to them to help achieve organizational goals.	1. Affective Commitment 2. Continuous Commitment 3. Normative Commitment	Likert
Human Relation (X ₂)	<i>Human Relations</i> is a human relationship between employees that gives rise to opinions, attitudes or behavior in a work situation that can encourage employees to be more productive at work and complete tasks according to work rules and have an impact on employee self-satisfaction both from an economic, psychological and social perspective.	1. There is communication 2. There is direction 3. There is openness 4. There is an attitude of mutual respect 5. There is loyalty	Likert
Motivation (Z)	Motivation is an encouragement both from within and outside a person that causes a person to want to carry out activities to achieve their goals.	1. Give back 2. Working conditions 3. Work facilities 4. Work performance 5. Recognition from superiors 6. The work itself	Likert

Source: authors' own elaboration

The results of the multicollinearity test show that the VIF and tolerance values are as follows: The Organizational Commitment variable (X1) has a VIF value of 2.048 and a tolerance of 0.488. The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the path model there is inequality of variance from the residuals of

one observation to another. If the variance from the residual from one observation to another is constant, it is called homoscedasticity, whereas if it is different it is called heteroscedasticity. With SPSS processing, the following results are obtained.

Figure 2. Scatterpolot
Source: authors' own elaboration

The scatterplot graph in the image above shows that the points are spread randomly and are spread both above and below the number 0 on the Y axis and do not form a certain regular pattern. This can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur in the regression model. So it can be concluded overall that the regression model meets the requirements of the classical assumption test.

The results of the analysis show that the direct influence that Human Relations (X2) has on Performance (Y) is 0.408. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of Human Relations (X2) on Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z), namely $0.500 \times 0.399 = 0.199$. So the total influence that the Human Relations variable (X2) has on Performance (Y) is the direct influence plus the indirect influence, namely $0.408 + 0.199 = 0.607$. Based on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the direct influence value is 0.408 and the indirect influence value is 0.199, which means the direct influence value is greater than the indirect influence value. These results indicate that indirectly the Human Relations variable (X2) through Motivation (Z) has a significant influence on Performance (Y).

Table 2. Total Influence Value

Influence	Direct Influence	Indirect Influence	Total Influence
1. Organizational Commitment → Performance	0,977	$0,633 \times 0,399 = 0,252$.	1,229
2. Human Relation → Performance	0,408	$0,500 \times 0,399 = 0,199$	0,607

Source: authors' own elaboration

The Sobel test is used to determine Hypothesis 6 and Hypothesis 7. The Sobel test is carried out to test the strength of the indirect influence of the Organizational Commitment and Human Relations variables on the Performance variable through the Motivation variable. To see the indirect effect, it can be done with a test tool, namely using the Calculation for the Sobel Test which is available by entering the original sample and standard error of each independent variable on the dependent variable if there is a mediator and without a mediator. With the criteria if the sobel test statistic is ≥ 1.96 with a significance < 0.05 , then this variable can be said to be able to mediate between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table 3. Calculation

Variable	Unstandardized	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Std. Error	P-Value
Organizational Commitment to Motivation	1.149 (a)	0.285 (S _a)	0.454	0.040	0.649
Motivation for Performance	0.016 (b)	0.035 (S _b)			
Human Relation for Motivation	0.571 (a)	0.204 (S _a)	1.588	0.029	0.112
Motivation for Performance	0.081 (b)	0.042 (S _b)			

Source: authors' own elaboration

From Table 3 above, the statistical test value of the influence of Organizational Commitment on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable has a statistical test value of $0.454 < 1.96$ with a significance of $0.649 > 0.05$, which means that Hypothesis 6 is not accepted where Motivation is unable to mediate the influence of Organizational Commitment on Performance. The statistical test value of the influence of Human Relations on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable has a statistical test value of $1.588 < 1.96$ with a significance of $0.112 > 0.05$, which means Hypothesis 7 is not accepted where Motivation is unable to mediate the influence of Human Relations on Performance. The Organizational Commitment variable has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the Rantau Selatan Labuhanbatu District Head Office. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Organizational Commitment has a significant influence on the Motivation of the Rantau Selatan Labuhanbatu District Head Office. This is supported by research conducted by Syarifah Ida Farida, Muhammad Iqbal, and Augustina Kurniasih (2016) with the title *The Influence of Trust and Organizational Commitment on Work Motivation and the Implications for Job Satisfaction*, Billy Santris (2019) with the title *The Influence of Leadership and Organizational Commitment on Teacher Performance with Motivation as an Intervening Variable at SMA Sutomo 1 Medan*, Andra Rofian Saputra (2018) with the title *The Influence of Compensation and Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance Mediated by Work Motivation Case Study at Hotel Merah Group Magetan, East Java, Indonesia*.

Conclusions

The Human Relations variable has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the Rantau Selatan Labuhanbatu District Head Office. The Human Relations variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.612, indicating that if Human Relations increases by 100%, it will increase motivation by 61.2%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Human Relations has a significant influence on the motivation of the Rantau Selatan Labuhanbatu District Head Office. This is supported by research conducted by Dwiyantri Rizki (2015) entitled *The Influence of Compensation, Work Environment and Human Relations on Work Motivation which is Relevant to Work Productivity (Study at PT. Morich Indo Fashion Semarang)*, M. Yamin Siregar and Amrin Mulia Utama Nasution (2010) with the title *The Influence of Human Relations on the Work Motivation of Employees at the Stella Maris Mother and Child Hospital (Rsia) Medan*. Based on the results of the Sobel test calculation, it is known that the statistical test value is $0.454 < 1.96$ with a significance of $0.649 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the Motivation variable is unable to mediate the relationship between the influence of Organizational Commitment on Performance. Thus it can be said that Organizational Commitment has no influence in improving Performance if done through Motivation. Based on the results of the Sobel test calculation, it is known that the statistical test value is $1.588 < 1.96$ with a significance of $0.112 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the Motivation variable is unable to mediate the relationship between the influence of Human Relations on Performance. Thus it can be said that Human Relations has no influence in improving performance if done through motivation.

Abstract

This research aims to find out whether Organizational Commitment and Human Relations influence Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable in employees of the Rantau Selatan Subdistrict Office. The research was conducted on permanent employees (PNS) at the Rantau Selatan Subdistrict Office. The population in this study was 30 people. Due to the small population, the sampling technique in this study was a saturated sample with a sample size of 30 people. The data collection technique used is primary data in the form of a questionnaire and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique uses quantitative data processed with the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this research show 1) there is a positive and significant influence between Organizational Commitment on Motivation, 2) there is a positive and significant influence between Human Relations on Motivation, 3) there is a positive and significant influence between the variable Organizational Commitment on Performance, 4) there is positive and significant influence between Human Relations on Performance, 5) there is a positive and significant influence between Motivation on Performance, 6) There is an influence between Organizational Commitment on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable, 7) There is an influence between Human Relations on Performance through Motivation as a variable intervening.

Список літератури:

1. A, Morissan M. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Survei*. Cet-2. Jakarta: Kencana.
2. Afandi. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Konsep dan Indikator)*. Yogyakarta: Nusa Media.
3. Afrian, D. (2021). *Pengaruh Human Relation dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Perkebunan Timbang Langsa (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Medan Area)*.
4. Alo, L. (1997). *Komunikasi Antar Pribadi*. Bandung: PT. Citra Aditya Bakti.

5. Anwar, S. (2011). *Metodologi Penelitian Bisnis*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
6. Arianto, N., dan Kurniawan, H. (2020). Pengaruh Motivasi dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *JENIUS (Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia)*, 3(3), 312-321.
7. Asrifah. (2015). Pengaruh Human Relations Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai di Kantor Wilayah Kementerian Agama Provinsi Sulawesi Tengah. *Jurnal Katalogis*, 3(2).
8. Astuti, D. (2022). Pengaruh Komitmen Organisasi Dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Manajemen Bisnis*, 2(2), 55-68.
9. Burhannudin, B., Zainul, M., dan Harlie, M. (2019). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja, dan Komitmen Organisasional terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Maksipreneur: Manajemen, Koperasi, Dan Entrepreneurship*, 8(2), 191.
10. Danang, S. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: PT. Buku Seru.
11. Davis, K., dan Jhon W. N. (2009). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
12. Effendy, O. U. (2009). *Human Relations & Public Relations*. Bandung: Mandar Maju.
13. Fahmi, I. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung: Alfabeta
14. Farida, S. I., Iqbal, M., dan Kurniasih, A. (2016). Pengaruh Kepercayaan Dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Motivasi Kerja Serta Implikasinya Pada Kepuasan Kerja. *Jurnal Kependidikan: Penelitian Inovasi Pembelajaran*, 46(1), 121-134.
15. Ghozali, I. (2005). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan SPSS*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
16. Ghozali, I. (2016). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program IBM SPSS 23 (Edisi 8)*. Cetakan ke VIII. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
17. Ghozali, I. (2018). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 25*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
18. Golung, H.D. (2013). Relationship between compensation, work environment, organizational culture, and employee performance at hotel Sedona Manado. *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 1(4).
19. Hasibuan, M.S.P., (2012). *Manajemen SDM*. Edisi Revisi, Cetakan Ke-Tigabelas. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
20. Hidayah, K. N. (2018). Pengaruh Human Relation dan kondisi lingkungan kerja fisik terhadap kinerja karyawan PT Sumber Abadi bersama Gondanglegi melalui variabel etos kerja (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim).
21. Kaswan. (2017). *Psikologi Industri dan Organisasi*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
22. Kreitner, R., dan Kinicki, A. (2014). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Edisi 9. Buku 1. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
23. Kuntjoro. (2002). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Rajawali.
24. Manery, B.R., Lengkong, V.P., dan Saerang, R.T. (2018). Pengaruh Komitmen Organisasi Dan Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Di BKDPDA Di Kabupaten Halmahera Utara. *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis Dan Akuntansi*, 6(4).
25. Mangkunegara, A. P. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
26. Miner, J. B. (1990). *Organizational Behavior: Performance and Productivity*. New York: Random House.
27. Moehersono. (2012). *Pengukuran Kinerja Berbasis Kompetensi*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
28. Nurandini, A., dan Lataruva, E. (2014). Analisis pengaruh komitmen organisasi terhadap kinerja karyawan (studi pada pegawai perum PERUMNAS Jakarta) (Doctoral dissertation, Fakultas Ekonomika dan Bisnis). *Jurnal Studi Manajemen & Organisasi*, 78– 91.
29. Nurjaya, N. (2021). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Hazara Cipta Pesona. *Jurnal Ilmiah Nasional*, 3(1), 60-74.
30. Riedel, A. G., Lengkong, V. P., dan Trang, I. (2019). Pengaruh Human Relation, job satisfaction dan job description terhadap kinerja karyawan Manado Quality Hotel. *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi*, 7(3).
31. Rizki, D. (2015). Pengaruh Kompensasi, Lingkungan Kerja dan Human Relations terhadap Motivasi Kerja Yang Relevan terhadap Produktivitas Kerja (Studi pada PT. Morich Indo Fashion Semarang). *Journal of Management*, 1(1).
32. Santris, B. (2019). Pengaruh kepemimpinan dan komitmen organisasi terhadap kinerja guru dengan motivasi sebagai variabel intervening pada SMA Sutomo 1 Medan. *Journal of Accounting and Management Innovation*, 3(2), 91-116.
33. Saputra, A.R. (2018). Pengaruh Kompensasi dan Komitmen Organisasional terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Dimediasi Motivasi Kerja Studi Kasus di Hotel Merah Group Magetan, Jawa Timur, Indonesia.
34. Sembiring, H. (2020). Pengaruh motivasi dan lingkungan kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan pada Bank Sinarmas Medan. *Jurakunman (Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Manajemen)*, 13(1).
35. Sinungan. M. 2016. *Produktifitas. Apa dan bagaimana*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.

36. Siregar, M.Y., dan Nasution, A.M.U. (2010). Pengaruh Hubungan antar Manusia (Human Relations) terhadap motivasi Kerja Karyawan Rumah Sakit Ibu dan Anak (RSIA) Stella Maris Medan. *Jurnal Konsep Bisnis dan Manajemen*, ISSN, 2407, 2648.
37. Sumarni, S., dan Pramuntadi, A. (2019). Pengaruh Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Perawat di RS PK Muhammadiyah Bantul. *Jurnal Manajemen Kesehatan Yayasan RS. Dr. Soetomo*, 5(2), 154-164.
38. Sutanjar, T., dan Saryono, O. (2019). Pengaruh Motivasi, Kepemimpinan dan Disiplin Pegawai terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *Journal of Management Review*, 3(2), 321-325.
39. Pratiwi, W. (2019). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Kelurahan Sertajaya Kecamatan Cikarang Timur. Cikarang.
40. Priyatno, D. (2014). *Mandiri Belajar Analisis Data dengan SPSS*. Yogyakarta: Mediakom.Kausal Loyalitas Pelanggan Toserba 'X'. Skripsi UPI: Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia. www.repository.upi.edu.
41. Robbins, P.S. (2006). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Edisi Sepuluh. Diterjemahkan oleh: Drs. Benyamin Molan. Jakarta: Erlangga.
42. Robbins, P. S. (2008). *Organizational Behaviour, Tenth Edition (Perilaku Organisasi Kesepuluh)*, alih bahasa Drs. Benyamin Molan. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
43. Sanjaya, P.K.A., dan Dewi, M.H.U. (2020). Lembaga Keuangan Mikro Adat Sebagai Penggerak Perekonomian Desa Lambing. *Widya Manajemen*, 2(2), 55–68.
44. Sanjaya, P.K.A., dan Saputra, I.P.J. (2020). Analisis Beberapa Faktor Yang Berpengaruh Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Badan Usaha Milik Desa (Bumdes) Gentha Persada Tibubeneng Kabupaten Badung: Ordinary Least Square Model. *Prosiding*, 2, 19–36.
45. Sinungan, M. (2016). *Produktifitas. Apa dan Bagaimana*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
46. Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, R & D*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
47. Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kombinasi (Mixed Methods)*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
48. Sutrisno, E. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan Kedelapan. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group.
49. Uno, H.B., dan Nina, L. (2012). *Teori Kinerja Dan Pengukurannya*. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara.
50. Wibowo. (2016). *Manajemen Kinerja, Edisi Kelima*. Jakarta: PT. Rajagrafindo Persada.
51. Winardi, J. (2016). *Manajemen Perubahan*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.

References:

1. Morissan, A. (2014). *Survey Research Methods*. 2nd ed. Jakarta: Kencana [in Indonesian].
2. Afandi. (2018). *Human Resource Management (Theory, Concepts, and Indicators)*. Yogyakarta: Nusa Media [in Indonesian].
3. Afrian, D. (2021). *The Influence of Human Relations and Work Environment on Employee Performance at PT. Perkebunan Timbang Langsa (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Medan Area)* [in Indonesian].
4. Alo, L. (1997). *Interpersonal Communication*. Bandung: PT. Citra Aditya Bakti [in Indonesian].
5. Anwar, S. (2011). *Business Research Methodology*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat [in Indonesian].
6. Arianto, N., & Kurniawan, H. (2020). The Influence of Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance. *JENIUS (Journal of Human Resource Management)*, 3(3), 312-321 [in Indonesian].
7. Asrifah. (2015). *The Influence of Human Relations on Employee Performance at the Regional Office of the Ministry of Religion, Central Sulawesi Province*. *Jurnal Katalogis*, 3(2) [in Indonesian].
8. Astuti, D. (2022). *The Influence of Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance*. *Journal of Accounting and Business Management*, 2(2), 55-68 [in Indonesian].
9. Burhannudin, B., Zainul, M., & Harlie, M. (2019). *The Influence of Work Discipline, Work Environment, and Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance*. *Jurnal Maksipreneur: Management, Cooperatives, and Entrepreneurship*, 8(2), 191 [in Indonesian].
10. Danang, S. (2018). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: PT. Buku Seru [in Indonesian].
11. Davis, K., & Jhon W. N. (2009). *Organizational Behavior*. Jakarta: Erlangga [in Indonesian].
12. Effendy, O.U. (2009). *Human Relations & Public Relations*. Bandung: Mandar Maju [in English].
13. Fahmi, I. (2017). *Human Resource Management*. Bandung: Alfabeta [in Indonesian].
14. Farida, S.I., Iqbal, M., & Kurniasih, A. (2016). *The Influence of Trust and Organizational Commitment on Work Motivation and Its Implications on Job Satisfaction*. *Journal of Education: Research on Learning Innovations*, 46(1), 121-134 [in Indonesian].
15. Ghozali, I. (2005). *Multivariate Analysis Application with SPSS*. Semarang: Diponegoro University Publishing Agency [in Indonesian].

16. Ghozali, I. (2016). *Multivariate Analysis Application with IBM SPSS 23 Program* (8th ed.). 8th printing. Semarang: Diponegoro University Publishing Agency [in Indonesian].
17. Ghozali, I. (2018). *Multivariate Analysis Application with IBM SPSS 25 Program*. Semarang: Diponegoro University Publishing Agency [in Indonesian].
18. Golung, H.D. (2013). Relationship between Compensation, Work Environment, Organizational Culture, and Employee Performance at Hotel Sedona Manado. *Journal of EMBA: Journal of Research in Economics, Management, Business and Accounting*, 1(4) [in English].
19. Hasibuan, M.S.P. (2012). *Human Resource Management*. Revised Edition, 13th Printing. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara [in Indonesian].
20. Hidayah, K.N. (2018). *The Influence of Human Relations and Physical Work Environment Conditions on Employee Performance at PT Sumber Abadi bersama Gondanglegi through Work Ethic Variables* (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim) [in Indonesian].
21. Kaswan. (2017). *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*. Bandung: Alfabeta [in Indonesian].
22. Kreitner, R., & Kinicki, A. (2014). *Organizational Behavior*. 9th ed. Book 1. Jakarta: Salemba Empat [in Indonesian].
23. Kuntjoro. (2002). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Rajawali [in Indonesian].
24. Manery, B.R., Lengkong, V.P., & Saerang, R.T. (2018). The Influence of Organizational Commitment and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at BKDPSDA in North Halmahera Regency. *Journal of EMBA: Journal of Research in Economics, Management, Business and Accounting*, 6(4) [in Indonesian].
25. Mangkunegara, A.P. (2017). *Human Resource Management of Companies*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya [in Indonesian].
26. Miner, J.B. (1990). *Organizational Behavior: Performance and Productivity*. New York: Random House [in English].
27. Moeheriono. (2012). *Competency-Based Performance Measurement*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada [in Indonesian].
28. Nurandini, A., & Lataruva, E. (2014). Analysis of the Influence of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance (Study on PERUMNAS Jakarta Employees) (Doctoral dissertation, Faculty of Economics and Business). *Journal of Management & Organization Studies*, 78-91 [in Indonesian].
29. Nurjaya, N. (2021). The Influence of Work Discipline, Work Environment, and Work Motivation on Employee Performance at PT. Hazara Cipta Pesona. *National Scientific Journal*, 3(1), 60-74 [in Indonesian].
30. Riedel, A.G., Lengkong, V.P., & Trang, I. (2019). The Influence of Human Relations, Job Satisfaction, and Job Description on Employee Performance at Manado Quality Hotel. *Journal of EMBA: Journal of Research in Economics, Management, Business and Accounting*, 7(3) [in Indonesian].
31. Rizki, D. (2015). The Influence of Compensation, Work Environment, and Human Relations on Work Motivation Relevant to Work Productivity (Study at PT. Morich Indo Fashion Semarang). *Journal of Management*, 1(1) [in Indonesian].
32. Santris, B. (2019). The Influence of Leadership and Organizational Commitment on Teacher Performance with Motivation as an Intervening Variable at SMA Sutomo 1 Medan. *Journal of Accounting and Management Innovation*, 3(2), 91-116 [in Indonesian].
33. Saputra, A. R. (2018). The Influence of Compensation and Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance Mediated by Work Motivation: A Case Study at Hotel Merah Group Magetan, East Java, Indonesia [in Indonesian].
34. Sembiring, H. (2020). The Influence of Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance at Bank Sinarmas Medan. *Jurakunman (Journal of Accounting and Management)*, 13(1) [in Indonesian].
35. Sinungan, M. (2016). *Productivity: What and How*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara [in Indonesian].
36. Siregar, M.Y., & Nasution, A.M.U. (2010). The Effect of Human Relations on Work Motivation of Employees at Stella Maris Mother and Child Hospital, Medan. *Journal of Business and Management Concepts*, ISSN, 2407, 2648 [in Indonesian].
37. Sumarni, S., & Pramuntadi, A. (2019). The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Nurse Performance at RS PK Muhammadiyah Bantul. *Journal of Health Management of Yayasan RS. Dr. Soetomo*, 5(2), 154-164 [in Indonesian].
38. Sutanjar, T., & Saryono, O. (2019). The Effect of Motivation, Leadership, and Discipline on Employee Performance. *Journal of Management Review*, 3(2), 321-325 [in Indonesian].
39. Pratiwi, W. (2019). The Effect of Work Motivation and Work Discipline on Employee Performance at Sertajaya Village, Cikarang Timur District. Cikarang [in Indonesian].
40. Priyatno, D. (2014). *Independent Learning Data Analysis with SPSS*. Yogyakarta: Mediakom [in Indonesian].
41. Robbins, P.S. (2006). *Organizational Behavior*. 10th ed. Translated by Drs. Benyamin Molan. Jakarta: Erlangga [in Indonesian].
42. Robbins, P.S. (2008). *Organizational Behavior, Tenth Edition*, translated by Drs. Benyamin Molan. Jakarta: Salemba Empat [in English].

43. Sanjaya, P.K.A., & Dewi, M.H.U. (2020). Traditional Microfinance Institutions as Drivers of Village Economy. *Widya Management*, 2(2), 55-68 [in Indonesian].
44. Sanjaya, P.K.A., & Saputra, I.P.J. (2020). Analysis of Factors Influencing Employee Performance at Village-Owned Enterprises (Bumdes) Gentha Persada Tibubeneng, Badung Regency: Ordinary Least Square Model. *Proceedings*, 2, 19-36 [in Indonesian].
45. Sinungan, M. (2016). *Productivity: What and How*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara [in Indonesian].
46. Sugiyono. (2018). *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research Methods*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta [in Indonesian].
47. Sugiyono. (2018). *Mixed Methods Research*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta [in Indonesian].
48. Sutrisno, E. (2016). *Human Resource Management*. 8th ed. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group [in Indonesian].
49. Uno, H.B., & Nina, L. (2012). *Performance Theory and Measurement*. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara [in Indonesian].
50. Wibowo. (2016). *Performance Management*, 5th ed. Jakarta: PT. Rajagrafindo Persada [in Indonesian].
51. Winardi, J. (2016). *Change Management*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar [in Indonesian].

Посилання на статтю:

Asrul Alamsyah Pasaribu. *The Influence of Work Discipline and Job Characteristics on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable* / Asrul Alamsyah Pasaribu, Sofiyan, Yeni Ariesa, Alex Tribuana Sutanto // *Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету*. – 2024. – № 2 (28). – С. 15-24. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.net.ua/ejopu/2024/No2/15.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.02.2024.2. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12746935.

Reference a Journal Article:

Asrul Alamsyah Pasaribu. *The Influence of Work Discipline and Job Characteristics on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable* / Asrul Alamsyah Pasaribu, Sofiyan, Yeni Ariesa, Alex Tribuana // *Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university*. – 2024. – № 2 (28). – P. 15-24. – Retrieved from <https://economics.net.ua/ejopu/2024/No2/15.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.02.2024.2. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12746935.

